

Tool wear and two-stage cutting investigation

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1. Introduction

This white paper examines the influence of progressive tool wear on sheared-edge integrity and the resulting formability of metallic sheets. The investigation comprises experimental sheet punching and hole-expansion tests conducted per the ISO 16630 Hole Expansion Test standard [1] and numerical simulations based on the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) framework described by Sandin et al. [2, 3]. The performance of a two-step punching strategy aimed at enhancing sheared-edge quality and sheet formability is also assessed. By combining experimental findings with computational modeling, this study provides a comprehensive evaluation of edge-damage progression and proposes practical tooling solutions for industrial sheet-metal processing. While Sandin et al. [4] investigates the influence of cutting clearance on sheared edge formability, this contribution rather focuses on the influence of tool wear and 2 stage cutting (shaving) on the cut edge characteristics and related ISO16630 hole expansion ratio (HER) properties.

2. Experimental procedures

In the present article, the 1.5mm CR700Y980T-CH automotive sheet steel by voestalpine Stahl GmbH was investigated in the cold rolled pickled and continuously annealed condition. This grade will be referred in the following as CP1000HD. This is a cold rolled complex phase steel with high ductility and an ultimate tensile strength of 1000 MPa. This material is common in automotive applications, such as crash management systems and structural components. The CP1000HD grade has a fine grained microstructure consisting of homogeneous bainite, martensite and retained austenite with a metallurgical concept similar to the one described in Chu et al. [5]. The mechanical tensile properties of the CP1000HD grade are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical tensile properties in different material directions relative to the rolling direction (RD) for CP1000HD with a thickness of $t = 1.5$ mm, yield strength ($Rp02$), tensile strength (Rm), uniform elongation (Ag), total elongation ($A80$), n-value at uniform elongation (nAg) and r-value determined at 4% elongation ($r4$).

RD	$Rp02$ [MPa]	Rm [MPa]	Ag [%]	$A80$ [%]	nAg [-]	$r4$ [-]
0°	893	1052	7.3	11.1	0.071	0.91
45°	905	1052	7.0	10.6	0.068	1.02
90°	909	1062	7.1	10.7	0.068	0.96

The experimental work presented in this article consisted of hole punching with varying process parameters, where the damaging effects from the cutting process were investigated. A subsequent hole expansion of the punched hole was used to obtain the cut edge formability properties. The experimental procedure is described in the following subsections.

2.1. Sheet punching

Sheet punching is a shear cutting process commonly applied in the sheet forming industry prior to hole collaring operations and for creation of bolt joints. This process produces a hole in the sheet using a fixed die and a moving punch according to the schematic image of Figure 1.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1: In (a) the servo-hydraulic machine used for sheet punching experiments. A schematic view of the sheet punching operation is shown in (b) for the initial step, prior to cutting, and in (c) the final step, after cutting.

The most significant process parameter of the hole punching process is the cutting clearance, which denotes the horizontal space between the punch and the die. Cutting clearance is expressed as a percentage according to Equation (1), where R_{Die} and R_{Punch} denotes the die and punch radius and t_{Blank} is the blank thickness.

$$\text{Clearance } [\%] = \frac{R_{Die} - R_{Punch}}{t_{Blank}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

The sheet punching experiments conducted in this work were performed using a servo-hydraulic clinching machine with 150 kN maximum load. The total press cylinder force was recorded with a calibrated 200 kN strain gauge load cell and the punch displacement was measured with a 100 mm Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) inductive displacement sensor. A total force of 5 to 15 kN was required for the blank holder spring device before punching. The punching piston speed, with a range of 0.05-55 mm/s, was set to 0.05 mm/s, corresponding to quasi-static loading conditions. A low cutting speed was chosen such that strain-rate hardening or adiabatic effect would not affect the results. The punching depth was adjusted so that the bottom dead centre corresponds exactly to the full material thickness. The punching of a 10 mm ISO16630 hole in the centre of a 100x100 mm sheet sample was made with a dedicated 4 columns

tool (Figure 1 (a)) with tight coaxiality specifications ($\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$) between upper and lower tool as well as high fitting accuracy for punch and die inserts ($\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$). This allowed for an accurate ($\pm 1\%$) cutting clearance compliance around the cut hole perimeter. The punching tools (punch and die) were made of high performance Vanadis 8/10 tool material with titanium carbonitride coating. The tools are suitable for hard cutting of UHSS grades with an optimum combination of high wear resistance, toughness and compression strength.

The effect of non-coaxiality on the ISO16630 test was previously reported by Levin et al. [6] and Larour et al. [7] as one of the main causes of the well-documented HER results scatter from this test. Due to this, the coaxiality of the ISO16630 HET cutting tool used in the present work was controlled by interrupted punching of a paper sheet. Figure 2 shows the results from paper punching where a slight unevenness in punch intrusion was detected. This caused some circumferential variation of the cutting clearance and consequently, the cut edge morphology, to be further discussed in Section 4.

Figure 2: Coaxiality test by paper punching, which shows a slight non-coaxiality through uneven cutting depth at 200 μm punch displacement.

To investigate the effect of tool wear, the edges of a die and a punch were artificially worn and sheet punching experiments with combinations of worn and new tools were conducted for 12.1 % cutting clearance according to Table 2. The actual edge shapes of the worn cutting tools have been used from representative microscope Keyence 3D 500X digital profiles since an idealised radius did not fit reality well. The shapes of the artificially worn tool edges were measured at an arbitrary point along the edges and the curvatures were digitalised, as shown in Figure 3 (a) and (c). For the numerical modelling of the tool wear cases, the radius and curvature of the worn tool edges were used. The numerical worn tool edges are shown in Figure 3.

Table 2: The load cases of the tool wear analysis conducted with 12.1 - 12.3 % cutting clearance, stating the name of the load case for further referencing, the cutting clearance and the condition of the tool edges.

Case	Cl.[%]	Punch cond.	Die cond.
Punch _{Sharp} - Die _{Sharp}	12.1	Sharp	Sharp
Punch _{Worn} - Die _{Sharp}	12.1	Worn	Sharp
Punch _{Sharp} - Die _{Worn}	12.3	Sharp	Worn
Punch _{Worn} - Die _{Worn}	12.3	Worn	Worn

Figure 3: The experimental and numerical tool edge geometry used for the tool wear analyses presented in Table 2. Images (a) and (c) show the experimental worn tool edges of the punch and die. Images (b) and (d) show the tool edge meshes of the worn punch and die.

Experimental investigation of two-step sheet punching, also commonly referred as shaving, was conducted using 5.3%, 12.1% and 20.5% cutting clearance. In contrast to the standard punching configuration, two-step cutting using an 8 mm or 9 mm pre-hole was performed for the mentioned clearances. The two-step punching experiments were performed using 400 kN blank holding force and 12% clearance for the punching of the pre-hole and followed by a hole expansion operation according to the procedure in Section 2.2, Table 3 states the two-step experiments and the associated parameters.

Table 3: Presenting the standard- and two-step punching experiments, with experiment case name, cutting clearance for the final punching operation, the pre-hole diameter $D_{H,1}$ and the final die diameter $D_{D,2}$.

Case	Clearance [%]	$D_{H,1}$ [mm]	$D_{D,2}$ [mm]
5.3 <i>Standard</i>	5.3	-	10.16
5.3 ₈₋₁₀	5.3	8	10.16
5.3 ₉₋₁₀	5.3	9	10.16
12.1 <i>Standard</i>	12.1	-	10.36
12.1 ₈₋₁₀	12.1	8	10.36
12.1 ₉₋₁₀	12.1	9	10.36
20.5 <i>Standard</i>	20.5	-	10.61
20.5 ₈₋₁₀	20.5	8	10.61
20.5 ₉₋₁₀	20.5	9	10.61

2.2. Hole Expansion Test

Determining the HER of the punched holes of varying clearances gave a relative assessment of the sheared edge formability. The HER were determined according to the ISO16630 standard using a 60° conical punch and burr-up condition, as burr-up is considered the worst case for HER values. The HET test is schematically shown in Figure 4, showing a symmetry cut of the test. As stated in the ISO16630 standard, the experiment was manually ended when the first visual through-thickness crack was observed. At this point, the HER was calculated according to Equation (2), where D_H was the average hole diameter at first through-thickness crack and D_0 was the initial hole diameter. The hole expansion test was performed for all cutting clearances cases in Table 2 and 3.

In spite of all drawbacks of ISO16630 hole expansion test, it has still been selected for the present investigation due to its simplicity and efficiency for some larger testing sample amount. The tests have been carried out with the same punching and testing machines, with the same operator, same laboratory and same punching and expansion parameters. The scattering has been minimised by punching and testing within maximum 15 minutes, since it has been shown by Carley-Clopton et al. [8], among others, that additional punch-to-test time delay can significantly reduce HER level and increase test scattering. The absolute standard deviation of HER values laid within 5-10% and was low enough to show with three replicates significant material related HER variation versus punch parameters beyond stochastic scattering.

$$\text{HER} [\%] = \frac{D_H - D_0}{D_0} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: A schematic image of the hole expansion test according to the ISO16630 standard with burr-up condition. The image shows half of the test setup, cut at the symmetry plane.

3. Numerical modelling

Numerical sheet punching models were developed based on the work by Sandin et al. [2], which utilises PFEM for axisymmetrical modelling of the shear cutting process. This section briefly explains PFEM and gives a description of the numerical modelling developed for modelling of the sheet punching cases in Table 2 and Table 3.

3.1. Numerical modelling of sheet punching

Two types of shear cutting models were used in the numerical work of the present article. One model performed conventional one-step punching, while the other consisted of two-step punching where a pre-hole was created in the pre-processing step. Schematic images of the two types of sheet punching models are shown in Figure 5, where (a) shows conventional punching and (b) the 5.3% cutting clearance two-step punching setup.

Figure 5: The PFEM models for (a) conventional sheet punching and (b) two-stage cutting. In (a) the punch and die diameter is denoted D_P and D_D respectively. In (b) the pre-hole diameter is named $D_{H,1}$ mm and the die diameter for the second cut is $D_{D,2}$. The tools are coloured dark grey, while the blank is light grey.

3.1.1. PFEM sheet punching model description

The numerical sheet punching models consisted of tools and blank. The tools were assigned a small strain elastic material model, while the blank was assigned the mixed formulation with a isotropic elastic-plastic model and a damage- and failure model. The axial position of the die part was varied to change the cutting clearance when modelling each of the cases of Table 2 and Table 3.

During the PFEM sheet punching simulation, the parameter h_{min} defines the minimum element size allowed by the re-meshing scheme. In this work a minimum element size of $h_{min} = 8.5$ [μm] was defined, giving a sufficiently fine SAZ discretisation at a reasonable computational time. Elements larger than 10 [μm] were incompatible with the sharp tool edge geometries, resulting in penetration in the tool edge contact. Meanwhile, elements smaller than 8.5 [μm] required more CPU-time, while producing cut edge morphologies similar to when using $h_{min} = 8.5$ [μm]. The initial discretisation close to the tool edges was defined to match h_{min} , as shown in Figure 6. Both geometrical and mechanical criteria were used for defining the areas of particle insertion or re-connectivity. These criteria are in detail described by Sandin et al. [2].

Figure 6: The initial PFEM discretisation for 12.1% cutting clearance, showing the symmetry axis and a magnified image of the SAZ mesh. The tools are coloured dark grey, while the blank is light grey.

For modelling of the 5.3% cutting clearance two-step shear cutting, the pre-holes of $D_{H,1} = 8$ mm and $D_{H,1} = 9$ mm were created in the pre-processing stage and not in a prior modelling stage. Thus, the pre-hole edge was undamaged in modelling of the second stage of the two-step cutting procedure. The numerical modelling setup for 8 mm pre-hole is shown in Figure 5 (b), showing the pre-hole diameter $D_{H,1}$ and the die diameter for the second stage of the cutting $D_{D,2}$.

4. Results and discussion

The following section presents and discusses the experimental- and numerical results obtained from the addressed methods of Section 2 and Section 3. First, an experimental hole expansion investigation declares the sheared edge formability assessment based on process conditions, such as cutting clearance, tool wear and two-step cutting. Then the following subsections presents results from sheet punching in terms of cut edge morphology, force response and grain rotation analysis and how they relate varying the process parameters and the sheared edge formability. The experimental sheet punching results are also used for validation of the numerical PFEM sheet punching model.

4.1. Sheared edge formability assessment

By the ISO16630 HET procedure presented in Section 2.2, HER values were determined for the punched holes presented in Table 2 and 3. Performing experiments with worn tools aimed to understand their effect

on the cut edge shape and edge formability. Conducting experiments with either a worn punch, worn die or both made it possible to investigate the effect from wear of the individual tool. Concurrently, numerical modelling of the worn tool cases demonstrated its applicability in, for instance, tool wear sensitivity analysis or tool edge shape investigation. By observing the HER values from sheet punching processes with worn tools, it appeared that the effect from tool wear was additive, where each tool wear case seemed to add onto the HER values. This is seen in Figure 7, where a significant drop of HER happened when using a worn punch (blue right point). Similarly, using worn dies reduced HER from the nominal (green left point). Using both worn die and punch caused the lowest HER of this investigation (green right point). The reason for the degrading effect of HER is thought to be the introduction of burr when using worn die and the increase of bending deformation using worn punch, which amplified the rollover formation. Such a behaviour on HER is also confirmed in a similar investigation on hot rolled CP800 AHSS grade by Gläsner et al. [9] with a gradual massive decrease of HER with either cutting punch and/or die tool wear experimentally simulated with a 250/500 μm artificially worn out die/punch edge radius.

Figure 7: HER values for 12% cutting clearance using cut edges with sharp tools and combinations of worn and sharp tools.

Table 3 presents a series of sheet punching experiments, conducted for 5.3%, 12.1% and 20.5% cutting clearance and with either standard one-step punching or two-step punching. The two-step punching were performed with a 8 or 9 mm pre-hole diameter. The holes produced were consecutively used in hole expansion tests in order to obtain the HER of punched holes. By doing this, the effect from two-step punching on the sheared edge formability was investigated. Figure 8 shows the hole expansion ratios from the experiments presented in Table 3. The most notable effect was discovered for the holes obtained using 5.3% cutting clearance, where it is seen in Figure 8 that one-step punching generated low HER while two-step punching caused a significant increase of HER using either 8 mm or 9 mm pre-hole diameter. The explanation to this was due to the avoidance of secondary burnish formation using two-step punching, further described in Section 4.2.

These results show how useful the two-step punching method can be for challenging sheet punching operations where unavoidable non-coaxiality or local low-clearance zones cause secondary burnish formation. For the larger clearances the positive effect of two-step punching was present, but not as drastic as for 5.3% cutting clearance. As shown in the publications by Stahl et al. [10] and Gläsner et al. [11], two-step cutting reduces the stiffness of the cutting scrap waste part in comparison to one-step conventional sheet punching. Two-step cutting has been proved most beneficial for reducing cut edge pre-damage and deformation in the SAZ by using a combination of minimised scrap width between pre-hole versus end hole as well as by reducing the cutting clearance in the following second end hole cutting. Narrow scrap with low remaining bending stiffness together with low subsequent clearance shaving minimises SAZ shear cut damage by transferring most plastic deformation into the scraped part and sparing the component hole cut edge from bending related damage, in comparison to one-step conventional shear cutting. Similar experimental findings for cold and hot rolled AHSS grades are found by Müller [12] showing that the two-step punching advantage for HER is best achieved when keeping the cutting clearance as low as possible in the second final cutting stage. This advantage is widely lost at clearances $\geq 20\%$.

Figure 8: The HER values from two-step cutting experiments shown in Table 3.

4.2. Cut edge morphology

Investigating the cut edge morphologies of the edges produced by shear cutting helped to give geometrical explanations to the sheared edge formability and how it varies with changing cutting clearance. Also, by comparing the numerical- and experimental cut edge morphology, the accuracy of the damage- and failure model was investigated since the distribution of cut edge parameters to most extent is controlled by the fracture process. The final cut edge results were defined in terms of rollover height, burnish height, fracture height and burr, i.e. the cut edge parameters and their respective distribution over the blank thickness.

Figure 9 shows the cut edge parameters from experiments and numerical modelling of the 12% cutting clearance cases with both sharp and worn tools, presented in Table 2. Similarly, Figure 10 shows the cut edge profiles from the corresponding cases. In the cut edge parameter graph and the cut edge profiles it is seen that a worn punch increased the rollover height at the expense of fracture surface height. The burnish surface height remained constant independent of tool wear. A notable result from the tool wear examination was the appearance of burr when using worn dies, no matter which punch edge shape. The material wrapped around the die edge, forming a burr even though the cutting clearance was 12% and no burr formed for sharp die edges. The numerical modelling was able to predict the tool wear effects on the cut edge, but over-predicting the burr height, most likely due the inexact worn edge shapes.

Such results match with the available literature, for example in the work by Gläsner et al. [9] and Magliaro et al. [13] with similar 800-1000MPa AHSS steel grades, reporting an increase in rollover, burnish, burr height and a decrease in fracture height with increasing tool wear. The present investigation more specifically emphasizes the often-underestimated specific role of die tool wear in critical burr formation for edge cracks. Distinguishing the influence of cutting punch versus die wear is important for an efficient monitoring of edge crack sensitivity of AHSS steel grades along a specific component industrial production life cycle. Both cutting punch and die should therefore be re-sharpened in maintenance operations, not just the moving punching tool.

Figure 9: Cut edge parameter results for 12% cutting clearance with different combinations of sharp and worn tools. Dashed lines show the experimental results and the solid lines show numerical results.

Figure 10: Experimental cut edge profiles (colors) and axisymmetrical numerically predicted cut edges (black) overlaid for tool wear analysis. Here (a) shows the profiles for sharp tools, (b) for worn punch - sharp die, (c) for sharp punch - worn die and (d) for both worn tools. The experimental cut edge profiles were determined at 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° around the punched hole circumference.

In addition to the HER graphs in Figure 8, Figure 11 shows the cut edge parameter results for the two-step investigation described in Table 3. For holes produced with 5.3% cutting clearance, the improvement of sheared edge formability using two-step punching is explained by the avoidance of secondary burnish. For the other cutting clearances in Figure 11, increasing the fracture height at the expense of burnish- and rollover height by two-step punching increased the HER values.

Figure 11: Experimental cut edge parameter results from experiments presented in Table 3 and the corresponding hole expansion ratio.

Numerical modelling of both one-step punching and two-step punching with 8- and 9 mm pre-hole

diameter was conducted for 5.3% cutting clearance, as presented in Section 3.1 and the numerical cut edge parameter results along with the corresponding experimental results are presented in Figure 12 (a). The cut edge profiles for the two-step results with 8 mm pre-hole are shown in 12 (b). Here it is shown how the numerical model was capable of predicting the positive effect from two-step punching by avoidance of secondary burnish formation. Such results enable the use of the numerical sheet punching model for process design and optimisation. Besides avoiding the harmful secondary burnish related notch formation, Figure 13 shows a pronounced reduction of total SAZ width in the cut edge bulk material when performing two-step punching compared to one-step punching. This effect was detected as a reduced area affected by plastic strain and was considered to have a positive effect on edge formability as the pre-straining of the cut edge is reduced. The positive effect of two-step punching on SAZ width and circumferential pre-strained SAZ volume was enhanced with the larger 9 mm pre-hole diameter. Two-step cutting is therefore a problem solving technology for challenging edge-crack prone industrial components. This comes however at additional cost and requires a good alignment between pre-hole and final hole cutting steps as well as an efficient scrap management.

Figure 12: Experimental- and numerical cut edge parameter results in (a) for standard one-step punching and two-step punching with 8 mm and 9 mm pre-hole using 5.3 % cutting clearance. In (b) the cut edge profiles from experiment and numerical analysis using 8 mm pre-hole are shown.

Figure 13: The distribution of plastic strain in the blank bulk material for (a) one-step punching, (b) two-step punching with 8 mm pre-hole and (c) two-step punching with 9 mm pre-hole determined by numerical modelling.

Figure 14 schematically shows the effect of clearance, tool wear and two-step close cut sheet punching on the cut edge morphology, relating to HER. This image shows how the reference HER variations due to increasing clearance is affected by either tool wear or introducing two-step punching. For instance, it is shown in Figure 14 how introducing two-step punching removes the secondary burnish formation and drastically increases HER, or how tool wear introduces burr even for optimum cutting clearances leading to a gradual HER decrease with increasing tool wear level.

Figure 14: A schematic graph summarizing the interacting effects of clearance, tool wear and two-step punching and how such parameters relate to both cut edge morphology and hole expansion ratio level.

4.3. Punching process forces and interrupted punching

Comparing the numerical- and experimental punching process forces enabled additional validation of the PFEM punching model. By observing the punch force versus displacement results from numerical modelling of the tool wear cases in Figure 15, it was possible to discern the effect of tool wear on process forces and

energy consumption. In Figure 15 it appeared that tool wear in general increased the process forces and prolonged the punch displacement. However, the increase of peak force and punching energy was significantly larger with a worn punch than for worn die, as stated in Table 4. It was therefore concluded that creation of rollover requires more energy than creation of burr. These results are in accordance with the work by Gläsner et al. [9] and Magliaro et al. [13], which clearly states that increasing cutting tool wear, manifested by rounding off punch and/or die edge radius, results in increasing maximum punching force, displacement and punching energy needed for the cutting process.

Figure 15: Numerical force versus punch displacement results from processes with 12.1-12.3% cutting clearances and combinations of worn tools.

Table 4: Experimental- and numerical results for the reference process with cutting clearance 12.1% using sharp tools and different configurations of tool wear. The table shows the punch displacement at fracture d_F from simulation, peak force F_{Max} , relative increase of peak force, numerical punching energy and relative increase of punching energy.

Case	Sim. d_F [mm]	Exp./Sim. F_{Max} [N]	Exp./Sim. Rel. inc. F_{max} [%]	Energy [J]	Rel. inc. Energy [%]
Punch _{Sharp} - Die _{Sharp}	0.50	33860/31558	0.0/0.0	14.35	0.0
Punch _{Sharp} - Die _{Worn}	0.54	34080/32584	0.7/3.3	15.78	10.0
Punch _{Worn} - Die _{Sharp}	0.59	34790/33836	2.8/7.2	17.72	23.5
Punch _{Worn} - Die _{Worn}	0.7	35590/34524	5.1/9.4	21.55	50.2

Concerning two-step punching, a significant decrease of punching forces was observed and presented in Figure 16, which shows in (a) the numerical force versus punch displacement curves, along with the experimental- and numerical peak forces in (b). Figure 16 (b) also shows the decline in process energy from numerical modelling when using two-step punching compared to the standard punching process. Table 5 displays the peak force values, punching energy and relative decrease of those values comparing standard one-step punching and two-step punching for the 5.3% cutting clearance case. Pre-cutting therefore reduces the necessary punching force and energy in the second cutting step. The larger the pre-hole diameter, the narrower the remaining scrap ring with less remaining stiffness and the easier the last cutting step operation can be performed.

Figure 16: In (a) numerical process forces for 5.3% standard sheet punching and using two-step punching with 8- and 9 mm pre-hole and (b) showing experimental- and numerical peak forces for the standard- and two step punching processes along with numerical process energy.

Table 5: Experimental- and numerical results for the reference process with cutting clearance 5.3% using standard one-step punching and two-step punching with 8- and 9 mm pre-hole. The table shows the punch displacement at fracture d_F from simulation, peak force F_{Max} , relative decrease of peak force, numerical punching energy and relative decrease of punching energy.

Case	Sim. d_F [mm]	Exp./Sim. F_{Max} [N]	Exp./Sim. Rel. dec. F_{max} [%]	Energy [J]	Rel. dec. Energy [%]
5.3 _{Standard}	0.45	34080/32748	0.0/0.0	15.9	0
5.3 ₈₋₁₀	0.40	32370/30096	5.0/8.1	14.3	10.0
5.3 ₉₋₁₀	0.36	30020/27090	11.9/17.3	13.1	17.6

5. Conclusions

This work presents a comprehensive investigation of the sheared edge damage, how it changes with varying process parameters and how it relates to the formability of the edge produced through close cut sheet punching. The article also gives a thorough validation of the PFEM sheet punching model by comparing experimental- and numerical results. From the results, the following conclusions were drawn:

- It could be shown as a guideline both experimentally and numerically that the maximum punch force decreases with increasing clearance, increases with increasing tool wear and decreases when applying two-step punching.
- The effect from usage of worn tools is accurately predicted by the PFEM model, which shows that a worn die can cause burr formation even at 12% cutting clearance. Such cutting clearance is normally considered the optimum cutting clearance with respect to cut edge formability and burr appearance due to worn die consequently diminishes the feasible range of cutting clearances.
- The study on two-step punching instead of conventional sheet punching shows that for low clearances secondary burnish formation can be avoided. The PFEM modelling shows additionally that the size of the total SAZ is significantly reduced. Both effects from two-stage shear cutting govern for a drastic increase of HER and two-step punching is therefore a useful process in particularly troublesome situations of sheared damage induced cut edge stretch flangeability issues.

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